

Factors associated with sustaining work with chronic spinal cord injury: a scoping review

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Purpose: Work participation remains challenging for people with spinal cord injury (SCI), as reflected in lower employment rates compared to the general population. To promote work participation for people with SCI, practitioners and policymakers need a better understanding of the factors associated with sustaining work in the long term. This study aimed to identify such factors.

Materials and methods: Scoping review synthesizing quantitative and qualitative research published between 2000 and 2021. The databases searched were PubMed, CINAHL Complete, PsycINFO, Scopus, and Web of Science.

Results: Initially, 1221 articles were identified. Three quantitative studies investigating socio-demographic and injury-related factors and eight qualitative studies exploring mainly personal and environmental facilitators and barriers to working in the long term were retained. The results of the quantitative studies showed the importance of time since injury, age and education. The qualitative findings emphasized the positive influence of self-advocacy, managing health behaviours and a supportive work environment. Main barriers were time organization and societal attitudes.

Conclusions: Future interventions should address the identified factors to promote working in the long term of people with SCI. Policymakers should adapt and enforce legal standards that address environmental and social barriers to creating supportive work environments for persons with SCI.

Keywords: working in the long term, sustained employment, work stability, spinal cord injury

Introduction

While identifying predictors for successful return to work (RTW) has become a major topic of rehabilitation research, knowledge on factors associated with long-term working of people with a disability remains scarce. Individuals with a physical disability, such as spinal cord injury (SCI), face major challenges in obtaining and maintaining employment [1]. Despite programs and policies designed to increase work participation after SCI, the employment rate of persons with SCI remains lower than for the general population [2,3]. Moreover, persons with SCI who return to work tend to leave the labour market before reaching statutory retirement age [4]. While the majority of individuals who sustain an SCI were employed at the time of the injury, only between 21% and 67% ever return to work or school after the injury [5]. According to a recent systematic review summarizing the results of 72 studies, on average 34% of individuals with SCI are gainfully employed [6]. This low average employment rate suggests that after returning to work difficulties in *maintaining* employment may arise.

Labour force participation is associated with higher earnings, better health, higher life satisfaction and longer life expectancy in persons with SCI [5,7-9]. Consequently, it is important that people with SCI are provided with better opportunities to rejoin the workforce. Factors associated with RTW after SCI include sociodemographic variables such as sex, race, marital status, education, disability status and work history (e.g. employment at or before injury) and injury-related characteristics such as age at injury, time since injury, level and severity of injury; and general health [5]. Other factors include functional abilities such as mobility and the use of transportation, psychosocial issues like life satisfaction, locus of control, motivational level and expectation to work, along with environmental factors including social support at the workplace [5]. Previous studies exploring employment followed participants for a limited period of time after the injury or included participants with a wide range of time since injury onset. Therefore, existing reviews on employment of persons with an SCI have not distinguished short- and long-

term employment nor have they directly addressed factors associated with working in the long term [5,6,10,11].

Time to return to work after SCI varies between studies and subpopulations. According to Ramakrishnan et al. [12], for example, 50% of study participants had returned to work within four years since sustaining an SCI. Krause et al. [13] report that of those persons with noncervical SCI who returned to a job different from their preinjury job 79% did so within 5 years. By contrast, for persons with cervical SCI the percentage was 50% after 5 years and 83% after 10 years. Factors that contribute to working in the long term may be similar to those that influence initial re-engagement with work, but their relevance may differ significantly. After the initial RTW phase has been completed, a person with a disability typically does not have the assistance of rehabilitation specialists [14]. Decisions about disability benefits, such as pensions and workplace adaptations, have long been made [15], and initial support for reintegration from employers and colleagues has probably faded. However, adjustment to the post-injury life situation for a person with SCI may take long beyond the initial RTW [16]. In addition, SCI-associated secondary health conditions, such as recurrent urinary tract infections, pressure ulcers and pulmonary problems, with a premature decline in physical performance due to aging, may increasingly affect their ability to work [17-19]. Person- and work-related characteristics as well as the social environment may determine whether a person with an SCI remains in employment in the long term or leaves the labour market prematurely. Therefore, the objective of this study was to identify the factors associated with sustaining work in the long term after SCI.

Methods

We conducted a scoping review following Arksey and O'Malley's [20] six-step framework. A scoping review is a method that provides a broad overview on the scope or coverage of available literature on a given topic [21]. The first step (i.e. the identification of the research question)

has been discussed in the introduction, the remaining five steps (identifying relevant studies; study selection; charting the data; collating, summarizing, and reporting the results; consultation) are explained in the following sections.

Identifying Relevant Studies

We conducted a comprehensive literature search in February 2021 using the following electronic databases: PubMed, CINAHL Complete, PsycINFO, Scopus and Web of Science. We also hand-searched reference lists of included articles and consulted grey literature (Open Grey, Google Scholar) to identify other potentially relevant studies.

The search strategy was adapted for each database and consisted of several terms related to SCI, work, factors associated with work, and their synonyms, joined by AND/OR Boolean operators (see Appendix). Where possible, we applied medical subject heading (MeSH) terms.

Study Selection

A priori, we decided to include quantitative and qualitative studies reporting on factors associated with working in the long term after sustaining an SCI. Only research articles in English or German were considered. Additional inclusion and exclusion criteria were then established post hoc during the literature search and informed by the emerging evidence from the preliminary search results.

Studies were selected based on the content-related criteria (i.e. the search terms as presented in the search strategy) and time-related criteria. Regarding the content-related criteria, we decided to include only studies dealing exclusively with paid work of working-age individuals (15-64 years [22,23]). By paid work, we mean competitive employment in the regular labour market. Competitive employment includes supported employment. Supported employment entails strategies and services that help people with a disability obtain and retain work in the regular labour market [24]. We excluded studies considering people involved in

sheltered work, vocational training or education as employed. Regarding the time-related criteria, for the quantitative studies we decided to focus on research involving participants who had a minimum time since SCI of 10 years. This decision was made because most studies do not report time since RTW or length of employment for their samples. According to the literature on RTW transition after an SCI, there is evidence that a majority of affected persons go back to work within two to seven years after their injury [12,13,25-27]. By extending this time frame, we intended to account for the initial RTW period and to ensure that most participants would have had the opportunity to gain some work routine. Therefore, for the purposes of our study, we defined working in the long term as being employed at 10 years or later after injury onset. For qualitative studies, we included studies with a focus on the experience of working in the long term or maintaining work, independently of the “ten-year post SCI onset” criterion. Additionally, we decided to include only studies published from 2000 onwards in order to focus on the contemporary labour market.

We imported the articles into an Endnote library and then transferred them to a Microsoft Access database to facilitate title/abstract screening. Two of the authors (MF and KK) independently screened all titles and abstracts against the predetermined and post hoc inclusion and exclusion criteria. Disagreements were resolved through discussion between the two authors. The same procedure was applied to the full text screening phase (figure 1).

<Insert Figure 1 around here>

Charting the Data

Study information including objective, study design, number of participants, main findings and factors associated with working in the long term after SCI were extracted and charted using MAXQDA [28].

Collating, Summarizing, and Reporting the Results

We summarized and synthesized factors associated with working in the long term, separately for quantitative and qualitative studies. The study findings were mapped to the corresponding components of the biopsychosocial model of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) [29] (see figure 2). For quantitative studies, KK extracted factors reported in the retained articles and assigned them to the components of the ICF model based on the refined ICF linking rules developed by Cieza et al. [30]. MF then verified the factors and their allocation. For qualitative studies, three authors with different professional backgrounds (KK: psychology and sociology, MF: physical therapy, BT: sociology) summarized and synthesized the findings in the following steps. First, KK identified factors impacting the participants' long-term work situation and categorized them to the components of the ICF model. Second, MF verified the factors and their allocation. Then, KK and MF grouped the identified factors within each ICF component based on their content relatedness and formulated specific themes. In the final step, themes were discussed and refined with BT [31].

<Insert Figure 2 around here>

Consultation

The final step of Arksey and O'Malley's framework is optional and relates to the involvement of key informants who are knowledgeable about the topic of a scoping study and may provide additional insights to those found in the literature [20]. In the present study, this step was omitted as one of the co-authors (RE) with extensive experience in the topic played the role of a key informant.

Results

Descriptive Characteristics of Included Studies

As indicated in figure 1, the initial search yielded 1221 articles. Ultimately, 11 articles were

included in the scoping review, three quantitative [32-34] and eight qualitative [35-42]. However, of the latter, four were based on the same study sample [9,35,36,40]. In the study conducted by Marti et al. [38], only 10 of the 15 interviewees fulfil our inclusion criteria. Therefore, we only included the results pertaining to these 10 interviewees in our analysis. From studies investigating factors related to both RTW and working in the long term, we only included the latter in our analysis. All studies were conducted between 2000 and 2018 and only involved high-resources countries: the United States (n=8), Switzerland (n=1), Netherlands (n=1) and Norway (n=1). Of the three quantitative studies, one was a cohort study with data collected at one, five and ten years post-injury [33]. This study reported information about work status of participants at a given point in time without indicating work duration or stability [33]. The other two studies had a cross-sectional design [32,34] (table 1). The qualitative studies provided more information on long-term work in terms of describing barriers and facilitators for job maintenance and stability. Five studies used focus group interviews [9,35-37,39] and the remaining three used individual interviews [38,39,42] (table 2).

<Insert Table 1 around here>

<Insert Table 2 around here>

Factors Associated with Working in the Long Term: Results from Quantitative Studies

The three included studies reported on several factors associated with the work status of people with SCI 10 years after injury.

SCI-related Factors

It has been reported [33] that a longer time since SCI onset was positively associated with being employed at the time of the study. However, a longer time since injury was also found to be associated with a lower chance of working in the long term [32]. Furthermore, the likelihood of early withdrawal from work increased for each year of advancing age at injury [32]. A lower

level of neurologic impairment (paraplegia) and lower scores on the American Spinal Injury Association scale (incomplete SCI) were positively associated with working in the long term [33].

Functioning-related Factors

The presence of pre-injury medical conditions [32] was negatively associated with working in the long term.

Personal Factors

The odds of competitive employment 10 years after the injury were significantly greater for “whites” compared to Hispanics and African Americans [33] as well as for men compared with women [33,34]. Similarly, Roels et al. reported higher odds of being competitively employed for men compared with women [34]. Younger age at the time of the study, higher education and having a stable relationship [34] were associated with a higher chance of being employed.

Factors Associated with Working in the Long Term: Results from Qualitative Studies

Qualitative studies revealed functioning, personal and environmental factors (see table 3). Personal factors were exclusively discussed in terms of psychological personal factors affecting working in the long term. We identified the following six themes: (1) self-advocacy, awareness and communication skills; (2) attitude of the person with SCI; (3) ability to adapt; (4) motivation and job satisfaction; (5) networking and having personal connections; and (6) self-management of health behaviours. With regard to environmental factors, three major themes emerged: (1) work environment; (2) services, health system and policies; and (3) social attitudes.

<Insert Table 3 about here>

Functioning-Related Factors

Secondary health conditions and ageing. Participants reported various functioning factors related to working in the long term. In some cases, end of employment resulted from aging and associated physical decline, such as fatigue, overuse of their shoulders from pushing on a wheelchair, or osteoporosis [40]. An early termination of work also took place due to changing impairments and evolving health demands associated with aging with SCI [40]. Several participants noted that prior to retirement, the time required to prepare and organize their daily routine increased due to progressing physical decline [39]. Additionally, working and aging with SCI negatively affected other areas of life such as family or leisure, resulting in leaving the labour market permanently [40].

Personal Factors

Self-advocacy, awareness and communication skills. The ability to be a good advocate of oneself was reported by two studies [37,40] as positively associated with working in the long term. Self-advocacy was considered crucial for asking for work accommodations. Study participants highlighted that they would only receive work accommodations if they actively asked for them. Self-advocacy was also essential to navigate the social security system and to receive the support needed to stay employed. People with SCI shared their experiences of how their rights were ignored when they did not stand up for them [37].

Awareness [35] and communication skills [40] were other factors mentioned in the context of self-advocacy. For instance, awareness of one's rights was considered a prerequisite to self-advocacy [35]. Furthermore, awareness of one's needs was the first step towards their fulfilment [35]. In the process of self-advocating, communication skills were described as crucial [35]. Additionally, persons with a higher injury level had to learn how to interact with

their assistants and caregivers [40]. Communication skills were also mentioned to be beneficial for networking and fostering personal connections [37].

Attitude of the person with SCI. People with SCI reported that having a positive attitude towards their disability and towards their work was a facilitator for them to stay employed [36]. “Having the perspective that work can be fun and engaging and then making choices to find that career or job environment that supports and energizes” (Reed et al. 2016 [36], pg.116) was particularly helpful to maintain work or return to work after sick leave due to secondary health problems. People with SCI highlighted that demonstrating a positive attitude impacts how others perceive a person, and therefore influences their willingness to help and support [36].

Ability to adapt. The ability to adapt to a new situation was mentioned in two ways. First, after the injury people with SCI had to “relearn” their bodies and their capabilities in order to adjust to post-injury reality [40]. Second, the development of a new employee identity was reported to be crucial in cases where a return to the pre-injury job was impossible [38]. The ability to combine skills from the pre-SCI job with vocational rehabilitation was another facilitator for working in the long term. People with SCI mentioned that during vocational rehabilitation they had learned new skills that, in combination with their pre-injury employment, had been crucial for finding a suitable post-SCI job [38].

Motivation and job satisfaction. Different sources of motivation were reported as positively associated with working in the long term [39]. Reasons to stay employed included financial benefits and the desire to maintain health insurance [39]. Salary was recognized as important per se, as a means to a better, more enjoyable life, and a way to support others such as being able to send children to school [41]. Additionally, promotions and recognition motivated people with SCI to work in the long term as it provided a feeling of self-accomplishment and positive feedback that enhanced self-esteem [41]. People with SCI stated that the encouragement from

family members motivated them to stay employed. Furthermore, having parents who have always been working builds a strong work ethic and the belief that everyone has to work to be a productive member of society. Later in life, being a parent motivates one to be a role model for one's own children and to promote positive work beliefs.

People with SCI reported different intrinsic sources of motivation to work. The desire to feel normal and being able to fit in with the rest of society and one's personal ambition and work ethic were reported as important [39]. People with SCI were motivated to work by the desire to change the misconception that people with disabilities do not, or cannot, work. Another reason for working was an ambition to contribute to and have an impact on society [39,41].

An important factor for working in the long term was job satisfaction and enjoyment felt from working. People with SCI mentioned that work provided them with a sense of purpose and fulfilment. It has been reported that salary and earnings do not compensate for the lack of job satisfaction and if the enjoyment from work decreases, there is a higher likelihood of people leaving their job [41].

Networking and having personal connections. Networking was mentioned as especially important for changing jobs. Relatives, friends and work colleagues were direct contacts to potential employers. They often prompt the prospective employer to focus on a person's reputation and skills rather than on their disability [37]. Personal connections with peers in the disability community were especially helpful in navigating the social security system and regulations.

Self-management of health behaviours. With regard to self-management of health behaviours, two subthemes emerged: management of health in daily life and management of psychological and emotional health.

Management of health in daily life. One's good health and proper health behaviours were

reported to be positively related to working in the long term [40]. People with SCI have to regularly perform health behaviours (like weight shifting to prevent pressure ulcers, bowel and bladder routine or exercises) in order to stay in good shape and prevent secondary complications [40]. These can take a considerable amount of time and effort and interfere with one's daily working schedule. Furthermore, working too much could compromise health behaviours and have a negative impact on health. The inability to conduct a health routine may result in secondary health conditions and terminate one's work life [40].

Management of psychological and emotional health. After returning to work, people with SCI must learn how to manage their psychological and emotional health in order to stay healthy and prevent fatigue and burnout. Strategies to achieve this new routine included paying attention to a healthy lifestyle, planning and performing health behaviours together with securing an adequate support system (e.g. health care plan, family members and friends) [36]. Other SCI-specific strategies included respecting one's feelings about the accident, taking a mental day off to deal with emotions and recovery, and willingness to transfer to a different, more manageable job, if needed [36]. One participant emphasized that one has to redefine one's priorities and make health the most important in order to avoid burnout and stay employed in the long run [36].

Environmental Factors

Work environment: work accommodations, colleagues and employer. People with SCI reported that a supportive work environment that met their needs and capabilities was crucial for staying employed. Accommodations at the workplace were mentioned in two contexts: firstly, changes related to their physical environment, like an adapted desk to fit knees and wheelchair underneath, wheelchair-friendly toilets, and accessibility of the working place (ramps and lifts). Additionally, technology-related assistive devices (voice recognition

software, a roller-bar on a keyboard, or an adjusted mouse) and transport technology (wheelchairs, hand controls, lifts) were important facilitators to working in the long term [39]. Secondly, accommodations related to job tasks and schedules, like flexible working hours and adapted/adjusted responsibilities [37,39]. Conversely, a lack of accommodations was reported as a barrier to staying employed. For example, one person mentioned that the pre-injury job required him to do multi-day business travel. After sustaining SCI he was not able to fulfil this requirement and thus it became a barrier to career advancement [37]. However, it has been reported that people with SCI may be reluctant to ask for job accommodations because of their fear of being refused or experiencing negative reactions from employers or co-workers [37].

Positive interactions with employers and work colleagues facilitate work accommodations and adjustments [37,40]. Having understanding work colleagues and a supportive employer facilitated staying employed, especially when dealing with secondary health problems.

Services, health system and policies. Factors related to services, the health system and policies emerged as important, albeit in different contexts. A good health care plan that allows for hiring a personal health assistant [37,42] and provides vocational rehabilitation, education and training was helpful both shortly after the injury and in the long term [37,42]. As mentioned by several participants, a reliable health assistant might be a prerequisite to getting ready for daily activities and maintaining employment [39,40]. In contrast, the lack of some services was mentioned as a barrier to working in the long term, for example transportation-related difficulties, like no access to transport, long commuting, or limited accessibility of the work place [37].

In terms of policy measures, two sub-themes were reported: policies that focus on individuals and those that focus on the environment [35]. Policies aimed at changing the environment by addressing discrimination, increasing accessibility or opportunities to work, by providing job accommodations, work incentives, defining disability rights, and modifying the

framing of disability were positively associated with working in the long term. People with SCI noticed declining disability-based discrimination over the years and an increasing accessibility of public spaces and work environments, which facilitate staying employed [35].

People with SCI had mixed views regarding social security policies. On the one hand, policies are highly appreciated as they provide a safety net in terms of a disability pension and health benefits. On the other hand, the same policies were reported to create barriers to increasing the number of hours worked because of the fear of losing benefits (financial disincentive) [35,38].

Social attitudes. Another barrier to working in the long term was discrimination because of disability, mainly based on myths and prejudices against people with disability [37,39]. Discrimination was related to judgments about limited abilities or physical appearance. One of the participants mentioned that people with physical disabilities are also perceived to have cognitive impairments [39]. By contrast, positive attitude of others was mentioned as an important facilitator of working in the long term [36, 41].

Discussion

We conducted a scoping review of quantitative and qualitative studies to identify the factors associated with sustaining work in the long term with SCI. Quantitative studies investigated the importance of SCI-related factors and socio-demographics, whereas the qualitative studies mainly identified functioning-related, personal and environmental facilitators and barriers to job maintenance. Quantitative evidence consisted exclusively of cross-sectional and longitudinal follow-up studies that provided insights into factors associated with individuals' work status at a given point in time after SCI onset, but not allowing for any conclusion concerning work stability.

Some of the factors identified in the current study are similar for both RTW and working in the long term. For instance, age at injury and education have long been identified as being predictive of RTW [3,5,11]. In the long-term perspective, the importance of number of years living with SCI [33] has been reported as significant, which seems to be related to learning and adaptation over time. As revealed by the qualitative studies, after sustaining an SCI, people need time to relearn their bodies and establish new daily routines, which means allotting sufficient time for recovery, performing health related behaviours that prevent secondary health conditions in the long run and then handling regular chores [40]. Such a “life-redesign” takes time and requires support from rehabilitation specialists and employers. Without proper adjustments, RTW tends to be neither successful nor long-lasting [43,44]. As shown by previous research, adjustment after injury needs to be individualized and well-tailored to the personal situation [44,45], while initial positive RTW experiences may have long-term benefits for patients as well as employers [43,46]. Taken together, the longer persons successfully manage their SCI, the better they master their daily life. However, it has also been reported that longer time since injury was negatively associated with working in the long term [34]. This could be explained by the generally older age of the study sample and longer time since injury (mean 22 years). As previous research has shown, work abilities tend to decrease earlier in persons with SCI because of secondary health conditions and a premature decline in physical performance due to aging [17,19].

The qualitative studies highlight the interconnectedness of personal and environmental factors and how they are important for working in the long term. For instance, self-advocacy, awareness and communication skills seem essential in successfully asking for job accommodations and soliciting needed support. People with SCI underlined that work accommodations were possible only because they asked for them. In case of refusal of such request, a person with such skills may be more successful in looking for a new job, as these personal skills are also helpful in networking and building personal connections. It has been

reported that good communication skills paired with a positive attitude facilitate interactions with employers and colleagues [36], and this is known to foster work accommodations [37,39,40]. These factors appear to be meaningful during initial RTW as well, but their relevance may slightly differ. For instance, in the early stages of RTW, a person with SCI may be willing to make extra efforts to meet work demands. They may also draw on personal resources to compensate for a lack of work accommodations. However, as shown by Reed et al., this strategy is not sustainable and in the long term may lead to burn out or secondary health conditions [36].

Persons with SCI are reported as being prone to burnout because of working excessively, which can be attributed to trying to overcome the disability and their ambition to work as hard and efficiently as other people. It has been highlighted that although people with SCI are aware of this risk and the importance of taking care of their health, they do not necessarily prioritize health activities [36]. As people with SCI age, proper self-management of health behaviours becomes particularly important. Aging and associated physical decline often interacts with late complications of SCI, such as pressure ulcers and shoulder pain, and may precipitate leaving the labour market prematurely [39,40].

While this scoping review reports factors related to working in the long term, it also points to the concept of “sustainable employment”. Sustainable employment can be defined as a work situation where a match between a person, the job, and the workplace supports the person to stay healthy and satisfied at work over time, and with a work performance that meets the expectations of the person and the employer [47]. The various indicators for a sustainable work situation can be considered as a requirement for successful working in the long term, and both are intertwined. It is important to not only consider time-related aspects such as work duration, but also subjective perceptions such as job satisfaction and factors related to one’s health and personal growth. As discussed above, initial RTW does not always equal successful working in the long term and sustainable employment. While returning to work can be seen as a first step

towards successful working in the long term, it is crucial to regularly monitor the match between the person and the job/workplace over time. On the one hand, the environment should complement a person with suitable work conditions, allowing accommodations and ensuring protection against discrimination based on disability [35,37,39,42]. On the other hand, achieving a sustainable work situation requires specific personal factors like adaptation to post-injury reality, building a new employee identity, learning capacity post-injury together with the necessary health behaviours [38,40]. Persons who are capable of self-managing their disability in all work-life domains have higher chances to remain employed. Others may require support or risk losing their job.

Sustainable employment relates to integrated disability management, that focuses on the coordination between different stakeholders to reduce the impact of illness and injuries, and supports employees in performing their jobs in the best possible way over time [48]. Integrated Disability Management (IDM) strategies aim to benefit both the employer and the employee by maximizing productivity and employee health [49]. IDMs do this by managing disability cases, coordinate benefits, and develop return-to-work programs. Thereby it supports both the employer and employee to navigate the tangled web of contracts, policies, procedures and past practices to ultimately create a supportive work environment. An IDM system framework ideally contains short-term (return-to-work) and long-term (stay-at-work) disability plans [50]. However, although SCI is acknowledged as a chronic health condition [51], in the studies evaluated for this review we found no evidence of active IDM long-term programs. This was the case even though people with SCI had expressed a need for support.

Strengths and Limitations

The main strength of this study is the synthesis of quantitative and qualitative studies. While the quantitative studies provided more robust information on “determinants” of working in the long term, the qualitative studies offered further insights into employment dynamics over time

and more in-depth information from the perspective of people with SCI. Notably, some factors associated with working in the long term were also found to be important for RTW, which provides a holistic picture on employment post-SCI.

However, our review also has limitations. Our search was limited to the selected databases and time coverage. Articles published before 2000 were excluded to focus on the contemporary labour market reality. Therefore, some factors might have been omitted. Additionally, we considered only articles in English or German due to the authors' proficiency in these languages, which might have excluded some studies. Furthermore, the lack of specific information on work duration after RTW in quantitative studies prompted us to use time since SCI as a time-related selection criterion, leading to two heterogeneous types of results in our review: factors associated with working in the long term reported by quantitative studies and barriers and facilitators for job maintenance explored by qualitative studies.

Implications for Rehabilitation Practice

The factors we identified in our review will benefit efforts in vocational integration and job retention strategies for people with SCI. Our data suggest the need to invest in better-tailored and long-term rehabilitation to successfully and sustainably reintegrate a person with a disability into the job market. Our findings may help to develop and implement integrated disability management programmes/plans and mobilize the essential external support that people with SCI need for maintaining employment. Any company could develop its own disability management strategy with an HR manager (or employer in small companies) who has a basic understanding of what it means to employ a worker with a disability and who regularly (at least once a year) checks if the work-conditions and the workplace are still adequate. Such a disability management plan is found to economically benefit companies if used for all employees, with and without disability, including aging workers [49,50].

Future interventions should focus on addressing modifiable factors associated with working in the long term through training, like education, self-advocacy, management of health behaviours and developing communication skills. Some of these factors were considered successfully in past intervention studies [52-55]. However, people affected by non-modifiable factors negatively associated with working in the long term should also receive adequate support. We suggest that rehabilitation practitioners pay close attention to people from marginalized and minority groups and those at older age to provide them with properly designed opportunities to participate in the work force such as through individual counselling and offering community-based employment coaching.

Implications for Future Rehabilitation Research

The current review shows that factors associated with working in the long term are closely related and interconnected to each other. Prospective cohort studies following persons from the time of injury across their life course would allow for a life-course understanding of what factors (or combination thereof) lead to working in the long term of people with SCI. Factors identified as important in qualitative studies such as communication skills, workplace adaptation or job satisfaction should be tested in hypothesis-driven longitudinal quantitative studies. Furthermore, studies involving different stakeholders would be beneficial to gain a comprehensive understanding of working in the long term. Studies that solicit input from employers and health professionals would provide valuable knowledge to develop return to work strategies at the institutional and policy level such as streamlining services and processes, minimizing bureaucracy, establishing return-to-work coordinators, and employing an early and durable multidisciplinary approach.

Future studies should use common guidelines when reporting characteristics of their sample, employment definition and work-related outcomes [3]. Our initial plan was to report on long-term employment and therefore we aimed to identify studies where individuals worked

continuously at least some years post-SCI. This was not possible due to missing information on post-injury work duration in most studies. Inclusion of studies with unspecified times since injury or with a limited amount of information concerning time to RTW precludes reliable interpretation and synthesis of the findings. Therefore, most of the initially identified quantitative studies had to be excluded. Detailed and standardized description would allow for meaningful data interpretation and enable comparison across studies.

Conclusions

Our review found that sustaining work in the long term after chronic SCI is an ongoing process that can be facilitated or hindered by various injury-related, functioning, personal and environmental factors. Those factors should be addressed to improve the work participation of people with SCI. Future interventions should focus on functioning and personal factors in order to effectively empower people with SCI to achieve and maintain working in the long term. At the same time, policymakers should invest in developing practical and legal standards to address environmental and social barriers to creating supportive work environments for people with SCI.

Word count: 5612

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Declaration of interest

The authors report no conflicts of interest.

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Table 1. Characteristics of the quantitative studies included in the scoping review.

NI= no information, NA= not applicable

Author(s), [Ref.], year, country	Objective	Methodological description Design (D); Source population (SP); Inclusion procedure (IP); Enrolment period (EP); Statistical analysis (SA); Measurement time point (MP)	Participants N; Type of SCI (etiology, level of injury, completeness); Gender; Current age; Age at time of injury; Time since injury;	Work outcome / Employment status at time of injury	Results
Arango-Lasprilla et al., [33], 2010, USA	(1) to determine if there were significant differences in the odds of competitive employment (versus not competitive employment) among Whites, African Americans, and Hispanics with SCI at 1, 5, and 10 years after injury; (2) to determine if there were significant changes in the odds of competitive employment (versus not competitive employment) over time within each racial/ethnic group; (3) to determine if there were significant differences in the changes in the odds of competitive employment (versus not competitive employment) over time between the racial/ethnic groups.	(D) Retrospective study (SP) Model systems patients with SCI enrolled in the National Spinal Cord Injury Statistical Center (NSCISC) database. (IP) 12468 participants initially selected 1378 subjects excluded due to missing employment data. (EP) enrolled into database 1973-1996 (SA) Assessment for potential bias for missing employment data, comparison of excluded vs. included participants, χ^2 , analysis of variance, repeated- measures logistic regression (MP) follow-ups 1, 5, 10 yr.	N = 11090 Traumatic SCI (paraplegia 49.63%; complete 51.53%) Gender: 83.69% male Current age: NI Age at time of injury: 28.86 (SD 9.40) Time since injury: 10yr Race/ethnicity: 70% white, 21 % African-American, 9% Hispanic.	Employment status: competitively employed (working) vs. not competitively employed (unemployed, homemaker, on-the-job training, sheltered workshop, student, and other/unclassified) Employed at injury: 69.07% Employed at 10 yr. follow up 30.38 % (N=1049 of total 3453) Employed at some point post-injury: 56%	Descriptive statistics: The race/ethnicity groups were significantly different with respect to age at injury, gender, preinjury employment status, preinjury level of education, marital status at injury, category of neuro-impairment and cause of injury Effects of adjusted model <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The odds of competitive employment at 10yr. after the injury were significantly greater for whites compared to Hispanics and African-Americans. Whites vs Hispanics OR 1.709 (1.196-2.44), Whites vs. African-Americans OR 3.022 (2.340-3.904), Hispanics vs African-Americans OR 1.768 (1.168-2.676) The odds of being employed increased significantly over time within all race/ethnicity groups. Gender (women vs. men OR 1.21 [95% CI, 1.07-1.38]), level of neurologic impairment (paraplegia vs. tetraplegia OR 1.87 [95% CI, 1.70-2.06]), ASIA impairment scale (incomplete compared with complete OR 1.52 [95% CI, 1.38-1.67])
Lidal et al., [32], 2009, Norway	To investigate the employment-situation of persons with SCI of long duration, living in a Scandinavian country, and To identify factors that might have influenced the participants in obtaining and sustaining employment after injury.	(D) Cross-sectional survey (SP) Participants more than 20yr. post-injury from a larger Norwegian investigation on traumatic SCI in 1961–1982. Work data from Statistics Norway (IP) 237 participants were contacted 179 agreed, 14 excluded or died. (EP) 2002-2004	N=165 Traumatic SCI (Tetraplegia, Frankle A-C=28%, D-E=8%; Paraplegia Frankle A-C=55%, D-E=9%) Gender: 82% male Age at injury: 23 (9.7) Current age: 50 (10.1) Time since injury: 27 yrs. (SD=4.3)	Employment status: competitively employed (working) vs. not competitively employed (unemployed, students, homemaker, on-the-job training, sheltered workshop, retired, and other/unclassified)	Factors significantly associated with not entering employment after SCI (OR [95% CI]) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The odds of not entering into employment after injury was OR 1.11 [1.06–1.16] for each year of advancing age at injury. Higher odds of not entering into employment for females vs. males 3.1 [1.2–8.5] Odds for not entering the workforce for tetraplegic vs. paraplegic 3.8 [1.7–8.5]

		(SA) Non-responder analysis. descriptive statistics, multiple Cox regression, logistic regression	Mean age at withdrawal from work 43 yrs. (13.0 SD)	Employed at injury: 58%, 22% students, 13% youth and children Currently employed: 35% Employed at some point post-injury: 65%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Odds for not entering the workforce for persons with functionally complete SCI (A–C) versus persons with grade (D–E) 15.7 [3.4–73.8] Risk indicators for early withdrawal from work after SCI. HR (Hazard ratio) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The likelihood of early withdrawal from employment increased for each year of advancing age at injury HR 1.05 [1.02-1.09]. The hazard ratio for early withdrawal from work was higher in persons injured after 1975 HR 2.09 [1.09-4.00] as well as for persons who experienced medical conditions prior to the SCI HR 4.38 [1.51-12.71].
Roels et al., [34] 2018, Netherlands	To analyze the relationships between different types of pain and work participation (WP) in people with SCI. To evaluate the relationships between self-reported pain-related limitations and actual WP. To investigate the relationships between age, gender, relationship, level of education, lesion level, time since injury, and WP.	(D): Cross-sectional Survey (SP); Patients participating in the Dutch multicenter research program Active Lifestyle Rehabilitation interventions in aging Spinal Cord injury (ALLRISC) Inclusion procedure (IP); 282 participants in the ALLRISC study were available, 265 participants with full data on pain and WP were included. Enrollment period (EP); Statistical analysis (SA); descriptive statistics, bi-and multivariable logistic regression analysis with WP as dependent variable, associations between WP and experienced limitations due to pain. (MP): ≥ 10yrs. post injury	N=265; Traumatic (91%) and Nontraumatic SCI Paraplegia: 59% Completeness: ASIA: A= 69%, B= 13%, C 9%, D= 23%, miss= 1% completeness); Gender male = 73% Current age; 47.9 yrs. (41.7-55) Age at injury; 18 to 35 yrs. Time since injury: 22 yrs. [IQR 17–31]; Pain types: musculoskeletal pain (N=165), neuropathic pain (N=117)	(WP): classified as employed, disability pension, retired, housekeeping, volunteer work, study/education or other. (Combinations possible) Hours of WP per week (non-workers 0 hr. per week vs. workers ≥ 1hr) 50% non-workers 30% ≥ 25 hr. per week	Pain was significantly associated with WP but relationship between type of pain and WP was n.s. in bi- and multivariable model. In bivariable analyses younger age at time of study OR= 0.96 [0.93–0.99], male gender OR 0.52 [0.30–0.91] and having a stable relationship were associated with higher chance of being employed. A longer time since injury OR 0.97 [0.95–0.99] was associated with lower chance of employment. Multivariable analyses confirmed findings from bivariable analysis. In addition, higher education was associated with a higher chance of being employed OR 1.79 [1.05–3.04] and OR 1.73 [1.01–2.97].

Table 2. Characteristics of the qualitative studies included in the scoping review.

Author, year, country	Objective/Research question	Study design	Participants	Results
Crewe, [42] 2000, USA	What have been the vocational experiences of this group of individuals with SCI? What developmental, personal, or social factors appear to have contributed to the vocational behaviour of the participants? How do participants describe the meaning of work in their lives?	Life story interviews with 50 participants from study conducted in 1974. Article presents vocationally relevant content from the two sets of interviews separated by 20 years (1974-1994).	N = 50 Gender: 86% male, all participants were Caucasian Age range: 39 – 77 yr. Time since injury: 22 – 45 yr. Injury level: 62% complete tetraplegia, 22% complete paraplegia, 16% ability to ambulate with assistive devices. 58% were married or in long-term committed relationships, 30% were single, 12% were divorced or widowed. Mean education level: 14.58 yr. 82% had engaged in remunerative work for a period of several yr. to more than 30 yr. after injury	Factors that contributed to the vocational accomplishments of this sample include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • early work experiences, • comprehensive rehabilitation services, • work ethic.
Wilbanks and Ivankova, [39] 2014, USA	To explore the factors facilitating adults with SCI rejoining the workforce in an urban area in order to identify items that may be emphasized in the rehabilitation process.	Semi- structured interviews and photography of assistive devices. Four adults who were currently employed participated.	N = 4 Gender:75% males (n=3), 25% female (n=1) Race/ethnicity: no information provided Age range: 42–57yr. Time since injury: 24 – 37 yr. Injury level: Cervical: 75% (n=3), Thoracic: 25% (n=1) Current work status: 100% full-time employment	Most common facilitating factors for staying employed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • motivation (intrinsic), • motivation (through family and professionals), • resources, • perceived benefits.
Meade et al., [41] 2015, USA	To identify the employment outcomes of greatest importance as defined by persons with SCI who have worked since injury.	Focus groups with a semi-structured interview format questions, at least 10 years post SCI. All participants had been employed at some point since injury.	N = 44* Gender: Male 70% (n=31), Female 30% (n=13) Race/ethnicity: White 83%, Minority 23% Current age, yr. (range, 30-73): 52.2 (10.05) Age at injury, yr. (range, <1-47): 21.57 (9.76) Time since injury, yr. (range, 14-58): 30.66 (2.83) Current work status: Working 50%, Not working 23%, Retired 27% Level of injury: Cervical 1-4: 11%, Cervical 5-8: 37%, Thoracic: 45%, Lumbar: 7%	Seven overlapping themes were identified under the 2 broad categories of compensation and subjective well-being. Category compensation: (1) salary and what it can support, (2) health insurance and other fringe benefits, Overlapping categories of compensation and subjective well-being: (3) promotions and recognition, Category: Subjective well-being: (4) social connection and support, (5) job satisfaction and enjoyment from working, (6) making a difference and helping others, (7) psychological and emotional health.
Meade et al., [40] 2016, USA	To examine the relationship between employment and behaviours associated with the management of physical health and functioning as described by individuals with SCI who have been employed post injury.	Focus groups with a semi-structured interview format questions, at least 10 years post SCI. All participants had been employed at some point since injury.	N = 44* Gender: Male 70% (n=31), Female 30% (n=13) Race/ethnicity: White 83%, Minority 23% Current age, yr. (range, 30-73): 52.2 (10.05) Age at injury, yr. (range, <1-47): 21.57 (9.76) Time since injury, yr. (range, 14-58): 30.66 (2.83) Current work status: Working 50%,	Main themes related to staying employed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • relearning your own body and what it can do, • general health and wellness behaviours, • communication, education, and advocacy, • secondary conditions and aging.

			Not working 23%, Retired 27% Level of injury: Cervical 1-4: 11%, Cervical 5-8: 37%, Thoracic: 45%, Lumbar: 7%	
Reed et al., [36] 2016, USA	To examine the relationship between employment and psychological health and health management as described by individuals with SCI who were employed at least once following injury.	Focus groups with a semi-structured interview format questions, at least 10 years post SCI. All participants had been employed at some point since injury.	N = 44* Gender: Male 70% (n=31), Female 30% (n=13) Race/ethnicity: White 83%, Minority 23% Current age, yr. (range, 30-73): 52.2 (10.05) Age at injury, yr. (range, <1-47): 21.57 (9.76) Time since injury, yr. (range, 14-58): 30.66 (2.83) Current work status: Working 50%, Not working 23%, Retired 27% Level of injury: Cervical 1-4: 11%, Cervical 5-8: 37%, Thoracic: 45%, Lumbar: 7%	Main themes related to staying employed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • adjustment and dealing with emotional reactions, • gaining self-confidence, • preventing burnout, • attitudes and perspectives.
Marti et al., [38] 2017, Switzerland	To examine work in the long-term pathways as experienced by individuals with SCI living in Switzerland.	Narrative interviews.	N = 15(10)** Gender: Male 80% (n=12) Age range: 30 -73 Age at injury (mean): 33.7 yr. Time since injury: > 10 yr. Level of SCI: Paraplegia 67% (n = 10) Completeness: Incomplete 47% (n = 7) Wheelchair dependent: 87% (n=13) Employed at time of the study: 47% (n = 9) Other health problems: yes 47% (n = 7)	The analysis revealed four employment pathways with the following characterizing factors: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) the pathway of no paid work: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "trapped" in pre-SCI employment identity, • problem orientation, • frustration with job search, • competing responsibilities, 2) the pathway of retraining: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • development of a new employment identity, • need for recognition, 3) the pathway of job adaptation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • desire to RTW, • combining skills from pre-SCI job and vocational rehabilitation 4) the pathway of continuing work: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • support of the pre-SCI employer, • vocational rehabilitation as a missed opportunity. <p>Factors associated with the pathway one "no paid work" were excluded from this review, because the individuals in pathway one never returned to work after SCI and therefore did not meet our inclusion criteria.</p>
Inge et al., [37] 2018, USA	To obtain perspectives of people with SCI regarding their perceived barriers to employment and the supports that they need to achieve their employment goals.	Focus groups, 31 individuals with SCI; 16 employed; 15 unemployed.	N = 31 (information provided by 26 participants) Age range: 25 – 63 yr. Time since injury (in yr.): 1 – 30 Race: Caucasian 73% Gender: Male 50 %, Female 50 % Injury level: no information Current work status: 52% employed (n=16), 48% unemployed (n=15)	Facilitators of employment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • learning to be a strong self-advocate, • acquiring job-specific training, • networking effectively, • putting necessary supports in place. <p>Barriers to employment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • transportation issues, • difficulties with accommodations, • perceptions of discrimination based on disability.

<p>Reed et al., [35] 2018, USA</p>	<p>To identify key components of programs and federal and state level policies which support employment outcomes, as perceived by individuals with SCI who have worked since injury.</p>	<p>Focus groups with a semi-structured interview format questions, at least 10 years post SCI. All participants had been employed at some point since injury.</p>	<p>N = 44* Gender: Male 70% (n=31), Female 30% (n=13) Race/ethnicity: White 83%, Minority 23% Current age, yr. (range, 30-73): 52.2 (10.05) Age at injury, yr. (range, <1-47): 21.57 (9.76) Time since injury, yr. (range, 14-58): 30.66 (2.83) Current work status: Working 50%, Not working 23%, Retired 27% Level of injury: Cervical 1-4: 11%, Cervical 5-8: 37%, Thoracic: 45%, Lumbar: 7%</p>	<p>Program components perceived to support employment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • support for education, • development of job seeking skills, including skills assessment, job placement, • practical experience, • instrumental support. <p>Themes related to policies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • policies focused on individuals, • policies focused on changing the environment. <p>Awareness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • importance of personal connections, • self-advocacy.
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* These studies report on the same study sample.

** Only the results pertaining to the 10 participants who had returned to work after the injury were included.

Table 3. Findings of qualitative studies, structured according to the ICF components and further specified by themes.

Functioning-related factors	
Secondary health conditions and ageing	
Factors positively associated with working in the long term	Factors negatively associated with working in the long term
	Low stamina [39] Physical challenges (body wearing out by working) [39] Secondary health conditions [40] Aging [40]
Personal factors	
Self-advocacy, awareness and communication skills	
Factors positively associated with working in the long term	Factors negatively associated with working in the long term
Communication, education [40] Learning to be a strong self-advocate [37] [35] [40] Awareness [35]	
Person with SCI's attitudes	
Factors positively associated with working in the long term	Factors negatively associated with working in the long term
Positive attitudes and perspectives [36] - attitude about yourself and your body [36] - attitude about work [36] - behaviours associated with attitude [36]	Negative attitudes and perspectives [36] - attitude about yourself and your body [36] - attitude about work [36] - behaviours associated with attitude [36]
Ability to adapt	
Factors positively associated with working in the long term	Factors negatively associated with working in the long term
Relearning own body and what it can do [40] Developing new employee identity [38] [41] Adaptation skills [38] Learning to live as a priority [38]	
Motivation and job satisfaction	
Factors positively associated with working in the long term	Factors negatively associated with working in the long term
Motivation for working [39] - extrinsic (social support, role models, financial incentives) [39] [41] - intrinsic (desire to feel normal, desire to work and be independent [39] [41], need for recognition [38] [41]) Job satisfaction [41] Early work experiences [42] Work ethic [42]	
Networking and having personal connections	
Factors positively associated with working in the long term	Factors negatively associated with working in the long term
Networking effectively [37]	

Putting necessary support in place [37] Personal connections [35]	
Self-management of health behaviours	
Factors positively associated with working in the long term	Factors negatively associated with working in the long term
General health and wellness behaviours [40] Psychological-emotional health [41] Preventing burnout [36] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - maintaining mental health [36] - vacations, sick days, mental health [36] 	Risk of burnout [36] Scheduling [39]
Environmental factors	
Work environment: assistive technology, work accommodations, colleagues and employer	
Factors positively associated with working in the long term	Factors negatively associated with working in the long term
Supportive work environment [39] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - physical work space and accessibility [39] - interactions with co-workers [39] [41] Support of employer [38] [39] Putting necessary support in place [37]	Transportation issues [37] Difficulties with accommodations [37]
Services, health system and policies	
Factors positively associated with working in the long term	Factors negatively associated with working in the long term
State rehabilitation resources [39] [41] [42] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a home health assistant [39] - assistive technology [39] Components of programs perceived to be significant in supporting employment [35] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - support for education [35] [41] - development of job seeking skills, including skills assessment [35] - job placement [35] - practical experience [35] - instrumental support [35] [41] Within policies, two themes were extracted: policies focused on individuals [35] policies focused on changing the environment [35]	Disincentives by the social security system [38] [41] Lack of services [37]
Social attitudes	
Factors positively associated with working in the long term	Factors negatively associated with working in the long term
Positive attitude of others [36] [41]	Overcoming myths and prejudices [39] Perceptions of discrimination based on disability [37] Negative attitude of others [36]